

Research Article

Gender Education Materials for Early Children

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Abstract: The purpose of this study was to find models and materials for early childhood sex education from a gender perspective. This study uses a qualitative method with a descriptive approach. The subjects in this study were students of the Joy Kids Elohim Babelan Kindergarten Bekasi. School data is taken from the Ministry of Education and Culture data reference. The students of Joy Kids Elohim Babelan Bekasi Kindergarten also studied moral education in which materials on sex education and body growth were prepared which students would later experience. Joy Kids Elohim Kindergarten Bekasi develops a gender education curriculum in which it discusses so that students are directed to the development of attitudes and knowledge about the most basic sex education that will be very useful for fortifying themselves from the threat of sexual violence. The results showed that gender education conducted by schools for students proved to be effective in increasing students' and parents' understanding of sexual violence. Improved understanding and skills training in designing methods for providing sex education materials to children are expected to be implemented for each child and disseminated through certain communities and organizations.

Keywords: Materials, Gender Education, Early Childhood.

Preliminary

Sex education is a very important part of education, giving the right material to help students is needed from an early age. Nadya and Syahrul (2021:165) explain that sex education given at an early age must have clear concepts, clear concepts will help make the material presented easy to understand. Sex education at an early age also needs to be done to avoid various deviations that can harm children and interfere with their development. The Indonesian Protection Commission (KPAI) at the beginning of 2018 explained that there were 117 cases of sexual violence against children, while throughout 2017 there were 393 cases. Even January 23, 2022 data through the www.kpai.go.id page explained that in 2021 there were 147 cases involving children's kindergartens with various cases including exploitation of child labor, child victims of economic exploitation, children as workers, child victims of sexual exploitation/ prostitution using networks, and victims of sexual exploitation/prostitution without networks.

The Government of Indonesia through Presidential Decree No.36/1990 dated August 28, 1990 explained 10 children's rights according to the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child, including: the right to play, the right to get an education Kindergarten, the right to get kindergarten protection, the right to get Kindergarten name (identity), right to get Kindergarten national status, right to get Kindergarten food, right to get Kindergarten access to health, right to get recreational Kindergarten, right to get Kindergarten equality, and the right to have a role in development. Referring to this view, it is clear that children in Indonesia have the same rights as adults, and as a whole, these rights must be upheld and respected. The rise of cases of violence against children is an indicator of how children's rights are not respected, Tri *et al.*, (2015: 436) the spread of sexual violence against children on the one hand remembers that kindergartens have an increase in

educators to build alertness. However, it is realized that being alert is not enough, but concrete steps must also be taken so that children recognize early on the dangers that may threaten themselves. Risa (2016: 55) "Discussing sex issues with children is not easy. However, teaching sex education to children must be given so that children do not go wrong in their lives. Sex education must be given by parents to their children as early as possible. Precisely starting when children are 3-4 years old, because at this age children are able to carry out two-way communication and can understand their body organs and can also be continued in Kindergarten introduction to internal organs".

Based on data on child complaints from the Child Protection Commission in Indonesia from 2016-2020 on pornography and cyber cases, there were 3178 cases of children, while cases of children as victims of sexual violence (rape/obscenity) in 2020 there were 419 cases, while in cases of trafficking and exploitation children in 2016-2020 there were 1409 cases. These numbers are not small numbers, Ali (2016:2) explains that the current rate of sexual violence does not only occur in adults or teenagers, but occurs in early childhood. The rise of cases of sexual violence needs to be handled intensively, one of which is by making preventive efforts through sex education from an early age.

Theoretical Review

Gender Education

Evi (2020:92) gender is a language used to emphasize biological differences between male and female sexes, but recently the word gender has a more specific meaning and is not only related to biological but also non-biological. Sexual harassment treatment that occurs in early childhood can be done by anyone, even of the same gender. Ateret and David (2020:2) explain that in a US national study of adult men and women, only 1% of women reported being harassed by other women compared to 83% of men who reported being harassed by other men. The sex of the perpetrator is important because it can affect the well-being of male survivors and the boys' disclosure process, as they report fear of being labeled as gay or a threat to their masculinity.

Gender education is so important for early childhood to be more aware of the various conditions that are in front of them, children must understand which touches are good and which are not good for themselves. Rizky and Pangung (2021: 969) When a child enters early childhood education, they immediately realize how the role and gender norms are accepted by others around them, for example in color stereotypes, children tend to choose blue for boys and pink for girls. Children learn to observe genders by watching and imitating what adults and their peers say and do. Nowadays, many parents also think that gender material is not appropriate for early childhood, while Asti (2010:8) explains her opinion that regarding the task of children's social development, as the person closest to their children, parents should provide simple guidance and explanations regarding identity, environmental conditions, especially gender issues. Children need to be given sufficient information and provide opportunities for children to learn and perform their roles according to the conditions in which they are. In this case, when a child is born as a boy, he acts as a man and if he is born as a woman, the child acts as a girl.

Gender Education Materials

Nadya and Syahrul (2021:167) introduce sex education in early childhood starting from when children identify their body parts, children know their body parts and functions. Children also understand the parts of the body that can be touched and cannot be touched by others, as well as the parts of the body that can be seen and which cannot be seen by others. Roziqoh (2014: 100) the process of implementing education from a gender perspective in early childhood is carried out through habituation, setting an example and not distinguishing between types of play for children. Risty (2017:2) sex education is a number of activities in conveying information in the context of forming attitudes about sex or gender as well as self-identity attached to children. Shofiatul and Lutfia (37:2022) in early gender education is education that needs to be taught and introduced well by parents and educators. People often think that early childhood does not properly understand

everything related to gender and will understand it by themselves over time. Even though this view is not appropriate to use, from an early age children need to know about sex education so that they recognize the changes that occur in their bodies and are able to avoid various possibilities of sexual harassment.

The provision of gender education must be adjusted to the age and characteristics of the child according to their gender, and provide an explanation of the parts of the body that can and cannot be touched by other people so that they can be careful. Siti (2019:226) sexual education is an educational program that involves Kindergarten students to get Kindergarten experiences related to specific health and various skills that can be used to avoid sexual problems in their environment.

Early childhood education programs

Tatik (2016: 50) early childhood is a group of children who are in a very unique and interesting process of growth and development, the process of learning and education in early childhood should be carried out with the aim of providing various basic concepts that are meaningful through real experience and allow children to be able to do activities and foster curiosity optimally.

Dameria and Melda (2021:105) convey that learning materials for early childhood require a variety of media in teaching. Media in teaching is needed in all lines of education, from early childhood education to higher education. In education the media used must be presented as attractively as possible, this is very helpful so that students can understand the material being taught and maintain student concentration.

Novrinda *et al.*, (2017:40) Early childhood education is very important to do since the child is born. This is reinforced by various research results that prove that providing education from an early age will shape brain development, health, help children's readiness for school, and children's social life. Of course there will be a very big difference in children who receive education from an early age compared to children who do not receive education from an early age.

Methodology

This study uses a qualitative method with a descriptive approach. The subjects in this study were students of Joy Kids Elohim Babelan Kindergarten Bekasi. School data is taken from the Ministry of Education and Culture data reference. Joy Kids Elohim Babelan Bekasi Kindergarten students also studied moral education which included sex education materials and body growth which students would later experience. Data collection methods used are primary data sources and secondary data sources. The premier data sources include Observation, Interview, Documentation, and Triangulation.

Results and Discussion

Sex education is an effort that should be given from an early age to reduce the number of victims of sexual violence against children. Education can be given when children are golden age or preschool children with an age range of 3-6 years which can be done formally or informally. Joy Kids Elohim Kindergarten Bekasi develops a gender education curriculum which discusses so that students are directed to the development of attitudes and knowledge about the most basic sex education that will be very useful to fortify themselves from the threat of sexual violence.

The sex education that students receive is also intended for teaching, raising awareness, providing information about caring for the body, and the parts of the body that students must take care of from an early age. The existing curriculum was developed using the methods of counseling and biology guidance. The theme of myself and the sub-theme of my identity and my body that students learn in it have entered the content of sex education according to the needs of children aged 4-5 years. The theme of myself is discussed and studied during 1 month of meetings and is discussed twice a week.

Table 1. Gender Material Activity Program

Weekly Activities	Development Aspect	Learning Materials
Activity 1-2 Week 1	Cognitive	Name, age, gender, address complete house Members of the body, parts of the members body, function, movement, hygiene, characteristics distinctive, health and personal safety
Activity 3-4 Week 2	Norms and Religion	Social and cultural norms that apply at home and at school Obligations and prohibitions of religion related to oneself
Activity 5 Week 3	Health	Personal hygiene, body parts, parts of the body, function, movement, cleanliness, characteristics, health and personal safety.
Activity 6-7 Week 3-4	Personality	Assertiveness 1) Children know the names of their body parts 2) Children know the function of each member of the body Self-efficacy Children accept the differences in male and female limbs

Through an activity program that has been prepared by the teacher, gender education materials are given to students in accordance with the activity program that has been determined by the teacher and agreed upon by the principal. As for the aspects of gender education material through the theme myself, the sub-theme of my identity and my body, some changes experienced by students are based on the results of the questionnaire as follows:

Table 2. The development of students' abilities

Gender stereotyping	Gender identity
a) There is a preference for the game gender-appropriate b) Performing gender stereotypes in activities, work and behaviour c) Boy playing inside large groups, girls in small groups or in pairs	Gender development goes through 3 stages: gender labeling, gender stability, and gender consistency

Meanwhile, based on interviews conducted with the parents of Joy Kids Elohim, they revealed that skimpy clothes on children are common in the environment. But now they are starting to realize that violence can increase the potential of Kindergarten children to become sexual victims. Parents' lack of awareness of potential dangers can be a contributing factor to the occurrence of sexual violence in children. The results of interviews with teachers indicate that the main obstacle for classroom teachers in providing sexual education to children is the limited language and materials they have. In addition, taboos in delivering material related to gender to early childhood are still an inherent culture and hinder the process of cognitive transfer to children. The class teacher also revealed that

the role of parents at home was also one of the factors that did not support the delivery of gender education to children. After the program was handed over and implemented in schools, parents no longer thought that sexual education for children should be given to children when they entered their teens. The teacher also revealed that through the programs provided by the teacher to students at school, parents are now good partners in carrying out the same program as at home.

Conclusion

The results showed that gender education conducted by schools for students proved to be effective in increasing Kindergarten students' and parents' understanding of sexual violence. Improved understanding and skills training in designing methods for providing sex education materials to children are expected to be implemented for each child and disseminated through certain communities and organizations. As for suggestions for activity participants, it is hoped that they will be able to disseminate information that has been obtained by Kindergarten during the activity process to the surrounding environment. Teachers are expected to be able to continue Kindergarten sex education programs through parent meetings which can be held at certain times.

Conflicts of interest

There is no conflict of interest of any kind.

References

1. Ariyanti, T. 2016. Pentingnya Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini Bagi Tumbuh Kembang Anak The Importance Of Childhood Education For Child Development. *Dinamika Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Dasar*, 8(1): 50-58.
2. Dianita, E.R. 2020. Stereotip Gender Dalam Profesi Guru Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini. *GENIUS: Indonesian Journal of Early Childhood Education*, 1(2): 87-105.
3. Gewirtz-Meydan, A. and Finkelhor, D. 2020. Sexual abuse and assault in a large national sample of children and adolescents. *Child Maltreatment*, 25(2): 203-214.
4. Hadianti, A. N. (2010). Pendidikan Gender Pada Anak Usia Dini. *Jurnal Penelitian dan Artikel Pendidikan*, 2(4): 18-25.
5. <https://bankdata.kpai.go.id/tabulasi-data/data-kasus-pengaduan-anak-2016-2020>
6. Jannah, S. and Bramastia, L.S. 2022. Urgensi Pemahaman Jenis Kelamin Dan Gender Pada Anak Usia Dini. *Thufuli: Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Islam Anak Usia Dini*, 3(2): 35-45.
7. Jatmikowati, T.E., Angin, R. and Ernawati, E. 2015. Model dan materi pendidikan seks anak usia dini perspektif gender untuk menghindarkan sexual abuse. *Jurnal Cakrawala Pendidikan*, 34(3): 434-448.
8. Justicia, R. 2017. Pandangan Orang Tua Terkait Pendidikan Seks Untuk Anak Usia Dini. *Early Childhood: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 1(2): 28-37.
9. Keputusan Presiden No.36/1990 tanggal 28 Agustus 1990 Konvensi Tentang Hak-hak Anak.
10. Maimunah, S. 2019. Implementasi pendidikan seks berbasis sekolah. *Jurnal Ilmiah Psikologi Terapan*, 7(2): 225-234.
11. Mukti, A. 2016. Pendidikan Seks Untuk Anak Usia Dini Perspektif Islam. *Jurnal Harkat: Media Komunikasi Gender*, 12(2): 89-98.
12. Ratnasari, R.F. and Alias, M. 2016. Pentingnya pendidikan seks untuk anak usia dini. *Tarbawi Khatulistiwa: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam*, 2(2): 55-59.
13. Ritonga, R.A. and Sutapa, P. 2020. Literasi dan Gender: Kesenjangan yang Terjadi di Tingkat Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini. *Jurnal Obsesi: Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini*, 5(1): 965-974.

14. Roziqoh, R. and Suparno, S. 2014. Pendidikan Berperspektif Gender Pada Anak Usia Dini. *JPPM (Jurnal Pendidikan Dan Pemberdayaan Masyarakat)*, 1(1): 86-100.
15. Sinaga, D. and Simorangkir, M.R.R. 2021. Understanding Early Sex Education through Image Story Media. *International Journal of Recent Innovations in Academic Research*, 5(8): 103-108.
16. Suhsmi, N.C. and Ismet, S. 2021. Materi Pendidikan Seks Bagi Anak Usia Dini. *Jurnal Golden Age*, 5(01): 164-174.

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